

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most typical is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. May be dark or light brown (cinnamon), generally even white. Not all the time black in color. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear may be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected beneath the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 toes in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, however their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They've pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are some of the best at climbing timber. Their relatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb timber for protection, food, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their weight loss program is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their diverse weight loss program offers them the power to live in a big vary of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the more than likely bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are responsible for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per year. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their spread-out nature and reduced habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the title of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt younger mammals resembling elk and moose. Their color varies from gentle blonde to darkish brown. The 2 subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 ft. □□ Food regimen: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on massive mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually bigger than those discovered within the Rocky Mountains because of a richer food regimen. Annually there are forty six assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Recognized for their aggressive behavior, grizzlies are responsible for essentially the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Dimension: Kodiak bears are almost as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight feet long, and 4 toes tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight loss program is much like mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, resulting from more plentiful meals sources, the islands can support a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to change into their very own subspecies. This has led to a more complex social construction which results in less conflict between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears could be aggressive. Due to their isolation, there is only one assault on people every different yr. Largest species of bear in the world weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is generally made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary in the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 ft tall. They are a threatened species resulting from loss of habitat from local weather change. Despite their monumental measurement polar bears may be fast, sustaining a 6 mph tempo within the water. □□ Options: In comparison with different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, narrow head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps received Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Diet: Their eating regimen consists principally of animals, particularly seals which they can smell from a mile away. Although they appear white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears could be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon because of the distant nature of their habitat. Identified for its cream color chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered weak. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Eating regimen: Depending on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries,

seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on humans are rising as folks encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Harmful? They are certainly one of the best bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), but Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found only in China. 99% of its food plan is bamboo. In fact, the second particular person in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas defending his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. ☐☐ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 remain in the wild and they're thought of a susceptible species. ☐☐ Dimension: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and might be over four ft tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at delivery. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical pattern in gentle brown and white. ☐☐ Diet: Not like other bears the panda's weight loss plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Features: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo retains them common: they poop over 40 instances a day! ☐☐ Harmful? Assaults are rare however dangerous, given that pandas have one among the best bite forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐ Location: The Solar bear is found in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain but considered susceptible and on the decline attributable to loss of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and different physique elements used in conventional medicines. ☐☐ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Features: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising sun. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Food plan: Sun bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In reality, they have an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Dangerous? As a consequence of its shy nature, assaults are rare. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the name sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of lower than 20,000, they are thought of susceptible. ☐☐ [very very big teddy bear](#) Dimension: They are fifty five to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Options: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're easy to inform aside from other Asiatic bears. In reality, they are very quick and might out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from bushes. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. ☐☐ Weight loss plan: Their food regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Dangerous? They're some of the aggressive bears, with probably the most attacks on humans, mostly on account of shock encounters. They blow the dust around with big puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and do not mix effectively with rhinos and elephants, often charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last brief-faced bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear to be glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Size: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to seventy nine inches tall. ☐☐ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final quick-confronted bear and the only bear native to South America. ☐☐ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Food plan: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a weight-reduction plan consisting of mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they may opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Harmful? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear behavior is nearer to the polar bear. They feature the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, just like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, but haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA tests had been unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas are usually not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in area. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their very own family which might be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR

SURROUNDINGS. Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that may indicate a bear is close by, by which case you want to be extra vigilant. Listed here are a number of ideas you should use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't accidentally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you might have great intentions, a bear is likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Secure YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP).** If you happen to see a bear, don't try to approach or feed it. This includes food, but also your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you select, make sure that it's at least 200 feet away from your tent so you do not attract bears to your campsite. 4. **Keep CALM.** When you meet a bear, don't run. Attempt to make yourself look as huge as possible, waving your arms above your head. You can also prolong a jacket above your head to make yourself look bigger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to dangle them up in a tree. Do not scream or try to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Battle Back.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play dead. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 feet lengthy, and 4.0 to 5.25 toes tall, the most important bear by both dimension and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Battle back with all your energy and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for essentially the most attacks. When in bear nation, it's all the time sensible to carry bear spray. It's properly deserved, particularly when cubs are around. Each year there are roughly forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to demise. In North America, grizzly bears have essentially the most fearsome repute. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per year. By way of raw chunk energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's bite reigns supreme. All bears are sturdy and to not be messed with. When using the chew drive quotient (chew energy relative to size), the sun bear packs essentially the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fire but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he grew to become an icon and to this day is the star of the longest-running public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear recognized for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous through-hikers to try and grasp the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a accountability-free lifestyle. He also is likely to be the primary bear to receive his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son often would visit on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near where he was from. Chris additionally wrote How to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

